

BY GLAUCO WINKEL

THE ELECTION OF PRABOWO SUBIANTO IN INDONESIA AND THE GEOPOLITICAL RISK FOR THE INDO-PACIFIC

POLICY BRIEF #23 DECEMBER 2024

COUNTRIES AND REGIONS: INDO-PACIFIC

What are the geopolitical risks for the Indo-Pacific with the new government of Prabowo Subianto? Subianto won Indonesia's presidential elections in the first round in February this year, receiving 96.2 million votes, corresponding to 58,6% of the total. He took office in October. The new president has a strategic perspective of Indonesia for the Indo-Pacific, as he translates national power into military power, proposes changes in Indonesia's insertion in its regional environment and aims to transform the country into a "global power" in green energy.

Firstly, the Subianto administration defined a strategy for the Indo-Pacific, linking national power to military power. The new government's strategic perspective on the regional framework in the Indo-Pacific points to a foreign policy that is critical of external interference in the region. As Joko Widodo's Minister of Defense (2019-2024), the Indonesian Armed Forces underwent an ambitious modernization programme, with a 15.1% increase in investment in the country's military sector in 2020. It is estimated that for the period 2024-2029, the program will receive investments of 46.6 billion dollars, mostly for the purchase of equipment and the construction of a national defense industry.

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Secondly, the memory of Subianto's role in Widodo's government also feeds the risks of a change in regional insertion. At the last summit of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), he met with the defense ministers of China and Japan, shifting the focus away from the bipolar axis between China and the United States. It should also be noted that Subianto's first international trips as president-elect were to China and Japan, respectively. In addition, Indonesia's new partnerships with Australia, South Korea and India strengthen the country's foreign policy in the Indo-Pacific, seen as the new pivot area of world geopolitics, as can be seen on the map.

SOURCE: PREPARED BY THE AUTHOR

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Finally, Indonesia’s new government aims to turn the country into a “global power” in green energy. In pursuit of this goal, Subianto plans to invest in bioenergy, hydropower, wind, solar and geothermal energy. To increase the effectiveness of these investments, he intends to reduce state bureaucracy, build dams and revitalize forests for bioethanol production. Moreover, his government will continue to impose restrictions on exports of strategic minerals, such as nickel, which is essential for the production of electric vehicles (EVs). Thus, Subianto will encourage the processing of these minerals within the country, with the aim of adding value to the final product and strengthening the country’s domestic industry.

1.2. RISK MATRIX

1.3. RISK MATRIX LEGEND

CODE	RISK	MACRO	STUDY OBJECT	MATRIX
R.41	RESTRICTIONS ON EXPORTS OF STRATEGIC MINERALS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION	INDONESIA	INDONESIA	
R.42	DESTABILIZATION OF RELATIONS WITH SOUTHEAST ASIAN COUNTRIES	INDONESIA	INDONESIA	
R.43	INDONESIAN MILITARY HEGEMONY IN SOUTHEAST ASIA	INDONESIA	INDONESIA	
R.44	INDONESIA’S COOPERATION WITH US MILITARY INITIATIVES IN SOUTHEAST AND EAST ASIA	INDONESIA	INDONESIA	
R.45	DESTABILIZATION OF RELATIONS WITH CHINA	INDONESIA	INDONESIA	

SOURCE: PREPARED BY THE AUTHOR

In short, it is understood that Prabowo Subianto's government must promote changes in the country's foreign and energy policy. Indications of this process include Subianto's recent role in ASEAN and Indonesia's closer ties with Indo-Pacific countries. The theme of advancing renewable energy, coupled with the country's energy self-sufficiency and transition, shows that Indonesia will be more open to foreign investment in this sector of the national economy. We therefore recommend that the Board of Directors, Senior Management and Investment Banks observe the geopolitical dynamics in the Indo-Pacific, especially Indonesia's rise in the region, and evaluate business and investment opportunities in the country's energy sector.

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